

ISic3363

Sikel funerary inscription

Language

Sikel

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Euboia

Place of origin (modern)

Licodia Eubea

Provenance

Necropolis at contrada Vigna della Signora; found October 1920, together with a second inscribed piece (ISic4391) and two uninscribed blocks

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 41697

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 50 cm

Width 98 cm

Depth 29 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. αδιομις

2. ραροιο

Apparatus

Text after Agostiniani 1992

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644868

Bibliography

Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche. Florence. At 124

Paino, Emma 1958. Nuova iscrizione sicula. *Kokalos*. 4: 163-168.

Agostiniani, L. 1992. Les parlers indigenes de la Sicile pregreccque. *Lalies*. 11: 126-157. At 150 no.12

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014